

saturated calomel electrode served for making electrical contact.

A Philips PR 9405 M pH meter was used along with a second saturated calomel electrode (S.C.E) as a reference and a salt bridge was used for electrode potential measurements. Measurements were made at $20 \pm 2^\circ$.

Results and Discussion

After conditioning of the electrode, the potentials for a series of standard solutions of lead nitrate were measured. A linear response was observed upto concentration $10^{-6}M$. The slope was found to be 25 mV/decade change in lead concentration. Below $1 \times 10^{-6}M$, a non-linear response was observed but the calibration curve could be utilised for determination of lead down to $1 \times 10^{-7}M$. Even with continuous use, the slope of the electrode remained constant up to eight weeks after which it decreased. However, a linear response was maintained even after three months.

To find the response time, the electrode was dipped in $1 \times 10^{-3}M$ lead nitrate solution and the potential was recorded at short intervals. A constant steady potential was reached within one minute. It required approximately 50–60 s for the potential to come within ± 1 mV of its final value.

Two sets of lead nitrate solutions were prepared, 0.1 and 0.01 M. pH of both the solutions was varied in the pH range 1–10 using either dilute nitric acid or a very dilute solution of sodium hydroxide. It was observed that the electrode potentials of both the sets of solutions remained unchanged in the pH range 2.0–8.0.

The selectivity coefficients K_{PbM}^{Pot} for seven cations were determined by the mixed solution method⁹ and the values obtained are: Cd^{II} (1.0), Hg^{II} (1.0), Co^{II} (0.01), Ni^{II} (0.01), Ca^{II} (0.005), Cu^{II} (0.005) and Fe^{III} (3.11). Thus the electrode can be used for determination of Pb^{II} in presence of Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} , Ni^{II} and Co^{II} ions.

Application: The electrode was used as an indicator electrode in the precipitation titration of lead nitrate with various anions like sulphate, chromate etc. Since lead sulphate formed is soluble so a partially non-aqueous medium ethanol-water (1:1) was used. A sharp change in the potential was observed at the equivalence point.

The estimation of the drug carbimazole involves the determination of sulphide which is subsequently converted into lead sulphide. Five tablets of drug were mixed with 1M KOH (50 ml) and heated at $250-80^\circ$ for 10 min. After cooling, sodium plumbite was added to obtain lead sulphide. The excess of lead in the solution was analysed by potentiometric titration with EDTA (0.01M) at pH 4.6 (acetate buffer) using the lead selective electrode as above.

References

1. H. HIRATA and K. DATE, *Anal. Chem.*, 1971, 43, 279.
2. E. PUNGOR, K. TOTI, G. NAGY and L. POLOS, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1983, 147, 23.
3. M. S. JOVANOVIC, M. DJIKANOVIC, B. D. VUCUROVIC and Z. ABRAMOVIC in "Ion-Selective Electrodes", ed. E. PUNGOR, Elsevier, New York, 1981, p. 257.
4. H. HIRATA and K. HIGASHIYAMA, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1971, 57, 476.
5. E. A. MATEROVA, A. L. GREKOVICH and N. V. GABUZOVA, *Obem. Ionometry (Russ.)*, 1976, 1, 137.
6. D. MIDGLEY, *Anal. Chim. Acta* 1984, 159, 63.
7. E. LINDER, K. TOTI and E. PUNGOR, *Anal. Chem.*, 1984, 56, 1127.
8. A. I. VOGEL, "Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 4th ed., ELBS, London, 1978, p. 468.
9. G. J. MOODY and J. D. R. THOMAS in "Ion Selective Electrodes", ed. E. PUNGOR, Akademiai Kiado, Budapest, 1973, p. 97.

Dehydration-Rehydration Behaviour of Zirconium Hydroxide and Aluminium Hydroxide Coprecipitated Hydrogel

N. K. MITRA*, P. GUHA and A. BASUMAJUMDAR

Department of Chemical Technology,
University of Calcutta, Calcutta-700 009

Manuscript received 25 March 1988, revised 6 June 1989,
accepted 27 June 1989

WATER¹ is a very important constituent of the hydrogel structure. Various physicochemical properties of the hydrogel depend on the quantity and orientation of the water molecules. During heat treatment of zirconium and aluminium hydroxide hydrogel, the speed of dehydration of one is influenced by the other². Mitra and Roy³ studied the effect of heat treatment of the synthetic aluminosilicate hydrogel below 200° and found evidences of gel skeleton collapse at higher temperatures⁴⁻⁶. In the present investigation, equilibrium dehydration loss experiments on zirconium and aluminium hydroxide coprecipitated hydrogels were carried out up to 600° and the above heat treated samples were subjected to rehydration at various humidities in order to study the structural flexibilities of the above hydrogel with respect to orientation of water molecules.

Experimental

Coprecipitated hydrogels of zirconium and aluminium hydroxide were synthesised by following wet interaction process of 5% aqueous solutions of $Al(NO_3)_3 \cdot 9H_2O$, $ZrOCl_2 \cdot 8H_2O$ (E. Merck; 99% purity) and liquor ammonia at pH 9 at $30-2^\circ$. After proper ageing the gels were processed to remove impurities as reported earlier⁵. The molar ratios of $ZrO_2 : Al_2O_3$ in the composition were kept at 1:3, 1:2 and 1:1 respectively.

Equilibrium dehydration – rehydration was studied by the previous procedure⁴. Weight-loss of each sample was determined after heating for 3 h in a muffle furnace. The heat treated samples were successively equilibrated for 24 h in a rehydration chamber at 35, 56 and 100% relative humidity keeping all experimental conditions same in order to have comparable results.

Results and Discussion

All the three coprecipitated hydrogels were at least partially crystalline in nature as evidenced by X-ray analysis which were carried out in a Phillips PW 1011 unit provided with a copper target. $\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiation of 1.5405 Å was used with nickel filter with 7 h exposure time. All the runs were conducted at 40 kV and 15 mA. The phases identified in the X-ray photographs (not shown) of the three coprecipitated hydrogels are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1 – PHASES IDENTIFIED IN ZIRCONIUM AND ALUMINIUM HYDROXIDE COPRECIPITATED HYDROGELS

Molar ratio of $\text{ZrO}_2 : \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$	Phases identified
1 : 3	Gibbsite syn, Nordstrandite, Bayerite syn type a, Bayerite syn, ZrO_2 in amorphous state
1 : 2	Nordstrandite, Bayerite syn type a, ZrO_2 in amorphous state
1 : 1	Nordstrandite, Bayerite syn type a, ZrO_2 in amorphous state

The results of equilibrium dehydration as a function of temperature of heat treatment are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2 – EQUILIBRIUM DEHYDRATION LOSS OF ZIRCONIUM AND ALUMINIUM HYDROXIDE COPRECIPITATED HYDROGEL ON PROGRESSIVE HEAT TREATMENT

Molar ratio of $\text{ZrO}_2 : \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$	Percent dehydration on heat treatment at (°C)					
	100	200	300	400	500	600
1 : 3	8.73	16.72	32.06	36.51	36.99	37.24
1 : 2	10.28	13.25	28.96	32.94	34.69	35.11
1 : 1	13.99	17.48	29.41	29.83	31.38	32.39

The results indicated that the dehydration was not continuous but proceeded in steps. Up to 200°, the dehydration proceeded slowly followed by a rapid rise up to 300° and fairly slowly increased till the final temperature of heat treatment. The inflexion point observed was independent of molar ratio of $\text{ZrO}_2 : \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$. Initially the magnitude of dehydration followed an inverse relation with the

Al_2O_3 content. However, beyond the inflexion point, particularly at 400° and above, the relationship was reversed. Thus it is seen that coprecipitated hydrogel having $\text{ZrO}_2 : \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ as 1 : 3, exhibited maximum loss on dehydration at 600°. It appears from the results that the loss observed at relatively high temperature resulted from aluminium hydroxide hydrogel, as on increasing the molar ratio it was reversed. It can also be observed

TABLE 3 – EQUILIBRIUM REHYDRATION OF DEHYDRATED COPRECIPITATED HYDROGEL ON PROGRESSIVE HEAT TREATMENT AT DIFFERENT HUMIDITIES

Molar ratio of $\text{ZrO}_2 : \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$	Percent rehydration on dehydration on heat treatment at (°C)					
	100	200	300	400	500	600
At 35% humidity :						
1 : 3	5.14	5.30	13.54	12.69	8.4	4.94
1 : 2	6.78	5.68	13.19	12.05	8.94	6.12
1 : 1	7.98	5.73	12.81	9.86	6.57	4.11
At 56% humidity :						
1 : 3	6.53	7.02	16.15	16.35	12.32	8.11
1 : 2	8.6	7.64	15.93	15.03	12.08	9.4
1 : 1	10.01	7.77	15.5	13.23	9.87	6.81
At 100% humidity :						
1 : 3	19.26	12.75	23.4	26.96	25.87	23.94
1 : 2	15.72	14.95	24.3	26.78	25.3	22.99
1 : 1	13.4	11.06	20.3	18.84	19.43	17.72

that the intensity of interaction of the water molecules associated with the gel structure was a direct function of temperature.

The dehydrated samples at each temperature were subjected to rehydration at three different humidities, i.e. 35, 56 and 100% and results are given in Table 3.

Rehydration was always found to follow a direct relationship with the humidity in case of hydrogels. But in the above system of coprecipitated gels, the magnitude of rehydration initially decreased on heat treatment which might be due to skeletal shrinkage of one of the components. At 300°, sharp increase in rehydration in all the molar ratios was noted. This was due to dehydration of $\text{Al}(\text{OH})_3$ up to the stage of active alumina which was very much susceptible to hydration. Then on further heat treatment, the rehydration capacity gradually decreased due to decrease in internal surface.

Conclusion : The physical identity of the individual species in the hydrogel was retained which is reflected through the observed dehydration – rehydration pattern as the object of coprecipitation was mixing in the molecular level retaining their individual characteristics. Dehydration proceeds in steps as in the early part of dehydration, the expelled

water mainly comes from $Zr(OH)_4$ gel and dehydration-rehydration follows a direct relationship with ZrO_2 content. On the other hand, in the latter part of heat treatment, i.e. at 300° and above, the linear relationship reversed due to dehydration of $Al(OH)_3$ hydrogel.

References

1. J. D. MACKENZIE, *J. Noncryst. Solids*, 1982, 48, 1.
2. W. G. SCHERER, *J. Noncryst. Solids*, 1987, 91, 101.
3. N. K. MITRA and K. L. ROY, *Trans. Indian Ceram. Soc.*, 1972 31, 87.
4. N. K. MITRA, S. GHATAK and S. MITRA, *Trans. Br. Ceram. Soc.*, 1977, 76, 6.
5. A. M. TAYLOR and R. ROY, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 4028.
6. L. P. VANREEUWIJK, *Am. Minerals, Part I*, 1972, 57, 499.

X-Ray Diffraction Studies on Coordination Polymer of Copper(II) with 2,5-Dihydroxy-*p*-benzoquinone

T. RAMKISHAN RAO and P. LINGAIAH*

Department of Chemistry,
and

LALITHA SIRDESHMUKH

Department of Physics, Kakatia University,
Warangal-506 009

and

SAFIA MEHDI

Regional Research Laboratories, Hyderabad-500 009

Manuscript received 6 June 1988, accepted 2 June 1989

THE study of coordination polymers started nearly four decades ago¹ and X-ray diffraction study of tris(1,2-diaminopropane)nickel(II) tungstate has been reported recently². We report here the

synthesis and X-ray diffraction study of coordination polymer of copper(II) with 2,5-dihydroxy-*p*-benzoquinone.

Experimental

2,5-Dihydroxy-*p*-benzoquinone was prepared by the reported method³ and its purity checked by tlc and m.p. An equimolar mixture of aqueous solutions of copper(II) acetate and the ligand was refluxed for 3-4 h on a water-bath. The resulting solid metal chelate polymer was washed with hot water, dried under reduced pressure for about 48 h and kept over P_2O_5 .

The elemental analyses were obtained from Microanalytical Laboratory, Calcutta. X-Ray powder diffraction data were recorded at Regional Research Laboratories (Hyderabad) on a Phillips diffractometer attached with a copper tube. The diffraction pattern was recorded at a chart speed of $2^\circ (2\theta)/\text{min}$ using the scale $2^\circ = 1 \text{ cm}$.

Results and Discussion

The elemental analyses of 2,5-dihydroxy-*p*-benzoquinone and the coordination polymer of copper(II) suggest the molecular formula to be $C_6H_4O_4$ and $C_6H_4O_4Cu$ respectively. The diffractograms of 2,5-dihydroxy-*p*-benzoquinone and the coordination polymer are presented in Figs. 1 and 2 respectively.

The diffractogram of 2,5-dihydroxy-*p*-benzoquinone consists of 17 reflections between 8° and $56^\circ (2\theta)$ with maxima reflection at $2\theta = 28.7^\circ$ which corresponds to $d = 3.14 \text{ \AA}$ (Table 1). The diffractogram of the coordination polymer of copper(II) records 11 reflections between 8° and $56^\circ (2\theta)$ with maxima at $2\theta = 17.2^\circ$ which corresponds to $d = 5.19 \text{ \AA}$ (Table 2).

Fig. 1. X-Ray diffractogram of 2,5-dihydroxy-*p*-benzoquinone.